

POLITICAL SCIENCES

ALBERDI 2.0: UPDATING THE 'BASES' FOR A NEW ERA IN LATIN AMERICA

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Abstract

This paper analyzes Juan Bautista Alberdi's fundamental work, "**Bases y puntos de partida para la organización política de la República Argentina**". We examine the historical and political context that gave rise to this work, as well as unravel the fundamental concepts proposed by Alberdi for the construction of a modern State. A central aspect of the analysis lies in the identification of Alberdi's ideas that have transcended Argentine borders, influencing the constitutional thought of other Latin American countries. In addition, the text reflects on the validity of these ideas in the current context.

Keywords: Latin America, liberalism, democracy, government.

Introduction.

In this work we address Alberdi's ideas and their relevance to the constitutional thought of the region, as reflected in his work "**Bases y puntos de partida para la organización política de la República Argentina**". We aim to analyze the historical and political context, examine the fundamental concepts proposed by Alberdi in "The Bases" and their relevance to political organization, and identify the ways in which Alberdi's ideas were adopted by other Latin American countries, and reflect on the validity of his proposals. In the book "**Bases**" "which includes a prologue by Farías Matías³ (2017) "...*Bases defined and conceptualized a new political time: from a retrospective reading, it meets all the requirements of a "classic". However, as Alberdi warned, it was published to "act", that is, to intervene in a specific situation with the expectation that the ideas woven into its more than thirty chapters could be transformed into a social, political and historical force. If Bases finally managed to become an "action book", perhaps "the" action book of the 19th century Argentina, it was because it offered a reading of history and*

a political project for that pivotal time that opened with the defeat of Rosas in Caseros..."⁴. In it he argues that the relevance of this classic work of Argentine and Latin American thought lies in how Juan Bautista Alberdi carries out a singular critique. His project of social and economic modernization is centered on the market, seen not only as an economic engine and symbol of freedom, but also as a moralizing agent and guarantor of a republican political organization. This project is articulated with responses to problems left by the revolutionary process and which, after the fall of Rosas, were crucial: the definition of the homeland, who governs, with what alliances, under what institutional scheme, with what objectives and in what historical context. If this analysis is correct, it can be concluded that "**Bases**" is a unique case in Argentine history in trying to unite, with tensions and paradoxes, economic liberalism with the constitution of the nation.

Investigation.

Editorial Evolution of Bases and starting points for the political organization of the Argentine Republic.

³ Ver Alberdi, J. B. (2017). *Bases y puntos de partida para la organización política de la República Argentina* (2da. ed.). p.7, Buenos Aires: Biblioteca del Congreso de la Nación. (Pensamiento del Bicentenario). [file:///C:/Users/USUARIO/Downloads/BasesAlberdi%20\(2\).pdf](file:///C:/Users/USUARIO/Downloads/BasesAlberdi%20(2).pdf) "...*Farías Matías (1978) profesor en Filosofía (UBA) Es*

docente en pensamiento Argentino y latinoamericano de la carrera de Filosofía (UBA) y en introducción a la cultura argentina y latinoamericana del Departamento de Economía de UN- PAZ..."

⁴ Alberdi, J. B. (2027), *ibidem*, p. 8

Juan Bautista Alberdi⁵

Moving forward in the reading of this document, the fundamental work of the Argentine thinker Juan Bautista Alberdi has experienced a remarkable editorial journey throughout its history. This evolution reflects the changing historical context and the intellectual development of Alberdi, offering readers a valuable window into his political thought.

First Editions: the work first saw the light in Chile in 1852, just three months after the Battle of Caseros, a crucial event in the Argentine national consolidation. This first edition, quickly followed by a second in the same year, marked the beginning of the dissemination of Alberdi's ideas on the political organization of the country.

French Editions: the third and fourth editions, published in France in 1856 and 1858 respectively, while Alberdi was fulfilling diplomatic functions for the Argentine Confederation, represent a change of scenery. These editions incorporated significant modifications: the second included a proposed constitution, while the third rewrote or added articles that harshly criticized the "secessionist" policy of Buenos Aires.

Reference Edition: The present version is based on the third edition, the last revised and corrected by Juan Bautista Alberdi, published in 1858 by Bensazón at the printing press of José Jacquin. This edition, considered the definitive one, reflects Alberdi's mature thinking on the political organization of Argentina.

The different editions of **"Bases y puntos de partida..."** offer invaluable testimony to Alberdi's intellectual development and his commitment to building a prosperous and democratic Argentine nation. Each edition provides a unique perspective on the author's ideas, contextualized in the historical and political framework of the time.

Each edition reflects the historical context and Alberdi's evolving ideas, and the differences between the editions are important to understand the development of his thought, while the third edition, the last revised by him, is the basis of this version.

In short, the study of the different editions of **"Bases ..."** allows a deeper and more nuanced understanding of the political thought of Juan Bautista Alberdi, a fundamental figure in Argentine history.

Fariás Martín adds that Alberdi proposes an innovative vision regarding the independence process and the political organization of the emerging South American nations. For him, independence is not limited to the break with the mother country, but requires the consolidation of a solid and prosperous State. Economic growth becomes, in this scenario, a fundamental element to achieve true independence.

In this framework, Alberdi makes a profound critique of the constitutional models of the past, considering them inadequate to respond to the needs of the new nations. Instead, he proposes an alternative model based on integration into the world market, thus seeking to promote economic development and strengthen the autonomy of countries *"... all the constitutions of the last period [...] have been made with internal views: sometimes [to] strengthen power in favor of order, other times to weaken it in favor of freedom; Spanish: sometimes [to] centralize the form of its exercise, other times [to] localize it: but never with the aim of suppressing in the constitutional law of the first era that which was contrary to the greatness and progress of the new States, nor of consecrating the means leading to the achievement of this great end of the American revolution [...]. In that period, when democracy and independence were the entire constitutional purpose, wealth, material progress, commerce, population, industry, in short, all economic interests, were accessory things, secondary benefits, second-order interests, poorly known and poorly studied, and worse attended to, of course..."*⁶. Based on these ideas, Alberdi criticizes the unitary constitutions of Latin America, particularly those of Argentina (1819 and 1826), Bolivia, Colombia, Mexico, Uruguay and even Chile. Alberdi argues that these constitutions established excessive restrictions and obligations for foreigners, thus discouraging both immigration and foreign capital investment.

⁵ Salduna B.(2023) Las ideas económicas de Juan Bautista Alberdi. Analisis., <https://www.analisisdigital.com.ar/opinion/2023/08/29/las-ideas-economicas-de-juan-bautista-alberdi>

⁶ Alberdi, J. B. (2017), *ibidem*, pp.14-15

The author argues that these limitations hindered the economic growth of the region, since they prevented access to the labor force and capital necessary for the development of depopulated territories. Alberdi emphasizes the importance of foreign capital as a fundamental driver of economic progress, considering that immigration, by itself, was not enough.

However, the author recognizes that the Chilean constitution, despite its unitary character, presents a different approach. Alberdi highlights the interest of this constitution in the construction of an order that favored the mitigation of internal conflicts. While this, for Alberdi, only created necessary, but not sufficient, conditions for collective prosperity, it represents a distinctive point within the panorama of the unitary constitutions analyzed.

Alberdi criticizes unitary constitutions for hindering economic development through restrictions on immigration and foreign capital. He considers that these elements are essential for the progress of Latin America, and highlights the case of the Chilean constitution as a possible exception within the unitary context.

The case of the Constitution of Mexico:

Alberdi's ideas in the Bases regarding the Constitution of Mexico said "...which should be encouraged by the great spectacle of the neighboring nation, has always presented to the foreigner who was to be its savior as a Mexican settler, a tenacious resistance and a bad disposition, which, in addition to its backwardness, have cost it bloody and disastrous wars. According to article 3 of its current constitution, which is that of October 4, 1824, the public exercise of any religion other than Roman Catholicism is prohibited in Mexico. To this day, the Mexican republic appears more concerned about its independence and its fears of foreigners than about its internal aggrandizement, as if independence could have other guarantees than the force inherent in the development of population, wealth and industry to a powerful degree. According to Mexican constitutional law (article 23), foreigners cannot acquire real property in the republic if they have not been naturalized in it, married to a Mexican, and, in accordance with the other provisions that the law prescribes relative to these acquisitions, they cannot transfer their property to another country. Spanish: movable property, but with the requirements and paying the fee established by the laws There the Spanish law governs (note XIII, title 18, book V, nov recopil) according to which foreigners domiciled or with a house of business for more than one year pay all the rights and contributions that the other citizens a law of February 1822 opens the doors of Mexico to the naturalization of foreigners, provided that they fulfill the requirements demanded by the law of April 14, 1828 These requirements, among others, are: that the applicant expresses to the city council one year before his desire to settle, and that he later proves, with a citation from the trustee, that he is a Roman Catholic Apostolic, that he has such a turn and industry, good conduct and other requirements. This system has led Mexico to lose Texas and California, and will perhaps lead it to disappear as a nation..."⁷. The author of the document argues that

Mexico should focus on its "internal aggrandizement," boosting the development of its population, wealth, and industry, rather than focusing solely on its independence and wariness of foreigners. True independence, according to the author, lies in the internal strength of a nation, not in exclusion and isolation.

The restrictive system toward foreigners has had consequences for Mexico, such as the loss of territories such as Texas and California. The author fears that, if this approach continues, the country could even disappear as a nation. In short, the document criticizes Mexico's restrictive policies toward foreigners, considering them as an obstacle to the country's progress and survival. It advocates an opening toward immigration and foreign investment, as key elements for economic development and the consolidation of the nation.

In the case of the Constitution of Paraguay, Alberdi points out "... Although there is no danger that the Argentine Republic will want to constitute itself on the example of Paraguay, it is part of my plan to point out the obstacles that contradict the law of progress in that part of South America, so closely linked to the prosperity of the neighboring republics. The constitution of Paraguay, given in Asunción on March 16, 1844, is the constitution of the dictatorship or omnipotent presidency as a definitive and stable institution; that is to say, it is an antithesis, a constitutional contradiction... [...] The constitution takes special care not to mention the word freedom even once in its entire text, despite being titled Law of the Republic. This is the first time that a republican constitution has been seen without a single freedom. The only guarantee that it grants to all its inhabitants is the right to complain to the supreme government of the nation. The right to complain is undoubtedly comforting, but it supposes the obligation to have reasons to exercise it. This regime is selfish, scandalous, barbaric, of a disastrous example and of no use to the cause of progress and culture of this part of South America. Far from imitation, it deserves the hostility of all the patriotic governments of South America..."⁸. The document criticizes the Paraguayan constitution of 1844, pointing out that it establishes a dictatorship disguised as a constitution. Although Congress theoretically has legislative power, the president has absolute authority, including the creation of armies and treaties, and control of justice and public administration, without responsibility or limits. Furthermore, the electoral system is a farce, since the president elects the Congress that elects him. The constitution keeps the country isolated and excludes religious freedom, perpetuating a permanent tyranny that prevents progress and benefits only the president.

The spirit of the new constitutional law in South America according to Alberdi "... from the foregoing review, we see that the constitutional law of South America is in opposition to the interests of its material and industrial progress, on which its entire future today depends. An expression of the American needs of yesterday, it is no longer in harmony with the new demands of the present. The time has come to begin its revision in the sense of the current needs of America. May the Argentine Republic, initiator of fundamental changes

⁷ Alberdi, J. B. (2017), *ibidem*, pp.72-73

⁸Alberdi, J. B. (2017), *ibidem*, pp.75-78

on that continent, have the fortune to open the new era by the example of its upcoming constitution! ... [...] ... It is not that the America of today forgets freedom and independence as the great ends of its constitutional law; but that, more practical than theoretical, more reflective than enthusiastic, as a result of maturity and experience, it is concerned with facts more than with men and does not focus so much on the ends as on the practical means of arriving at the truth of those ends. Today we are seeking the practical reality of what in other times we were content to proclaim and write. This is the purpose of today's constitutions: they must aim to organize and establish the great practical means of removing emancipated America from the dark and subordinate state in which it finds itself... ”⁹.

In this section, the author analyzes the need to reorient the priorities of South American nations within the framework of their constitutions. He proposes an approach that prioritizes material development as a fundamental pillar for the consolidation of independence and the freedoms achieved. Thus, he argues that while independence, freedom and worship are fundamental principles, in the current situation it is essential to focus on other elements for their effective realization. In this sense, the importance of promoting free immigration, increasing the population in the vast territories of the region; promoting free trade, stimulating economic growth and the generation of wealth; developing transportation infrastructure, implementing railway networks to connect the regions and facilitate commercial exchange; promoting industry without restrictions, promoting industrial development to achieve economic self-sufficiency is highlighted.

It is argued that, like individuals, nations must focus first on their material development and then achieve higher goals. In this sense, constitutions must be instruments adaptable to changing circumstances, reflecting the needs of the present and not of the past or the future.

It is proposed to conceive the South American constitutions as "scaffolding" in the construction of the political edifice, flexible tools that adjust to the changing needs of the region. Therefore, the transitory and creative nature that constitutions must have in this stage of initial development and consolidation of independence is highlighted.

As we advance in the reading of the document, another relevant topic that Alberdi addresses has to do with Education is not Instruction “... *Belgrano, Bolívar, Egaña and Rivadavia understood from their time that only through education would these people one day become worthy of the form of government that necessity imposed on them in advance, but they confused education with instruction, genus with species, trees are susceptible to education; but only rational beings are instructed...[...]. In our instruction plans we must flee from sophists, who make demagogues, and from monasticism, which makes slaves and concealed characters. Let the clergy educate itself, but not take charge of forming our lawyers and statesmen, our businessmen, sailors and warriors... ”*¹⁰.

The text criticizes the education provided in South American towns, arguing that it has been inappropriate and sterile by copying foreign models without considering local needs. Primary education has been harmful, and higher education, instead of training useful professionals, has produced charlatans and demagogues. The importance of practical education is highlighted, focused on applied sciences, industry and modern languages such as English, instead of abstract subjects. The author advocates training engineers and technical professionals who can develop infrastructure and improve the material conditions of the continent. In addition, he emphasizes that morality and order arise from industry and productivity. An educational approach is proposed that forms productive and morally solid citizens, adapted to the specific needs of South America.

Regarding The civilizing action of Europe in the Republics of South America Alberdi adds: “... *the republics of South America are the product and living testimony of the action of Europe in America. What we call independent America is nothing more than Europe established in America; and our revolution is nothing other than the dismemberment of a European power into two halves, which today manage themselves. Everything in the civilization of our soil is European; America itself is a European discovery. It was brought to light by a Genoese navigator, and the discovery was fostered by a sovereign of Spain. Cortes, Pizarro, Mendoza, Valdivia, who were not born in America, populated it with the people who own it today, who are certainly not indigenous. We do not have a single important city that was not founded by Europeans. Santiago was founded by a foreigner named Pedro Valdivia, and Buenos Aires by another foreigner named Pedro de Mendoza. All our important cities received European names from their foreign founders. The very name of America was taken from one of those foreign discoverers: Amerigo Vespucci, from Florence... ”*¹¹. Furthermore, the document points out that even after independence, indigenous people do not form a significant part of political and civil society, and that those who call themselves Americans are actually Europeans born in America. Culture, religion, language and laws in South America are European. The real division in South America is between Europeans and non-Europeans, with Europeans being the ones who have brought civilization to the continent. Furthermore, it criticizes the aversion to foreigners, considering it a cause of ruin and an obstacle to progress. It advocates recognizing the continued influence of Europe and seeking its help again to complete American culture.

It also addresses the need to combat the dissolution of Spanish society by using the credulity and truth that are within the reach of the masses. It stresses the importance of asking the people whether they consider themselves to be of indigenous race or descendants of savages, and reminding them that civilization and the religion of Jesus Christ were brought by foreign races. The text questions the patriots of the early period for not understanding the new needs of the continent,

⁹ Alberdi, J. B. (2017), *ibidem*, pp.78-79

¹⁰ Alberdi, J. B. (2017), *ibidem*, pp.86-88

¹¹ Alberdi, J. B. (2017), *ibidem*, p. 91

which were focused on military glory rather than progress. However, the need for population and prosperity, which will come from Europe as before, is emphasized, and a sublime hope is expressed for the future improvement of America.

Findings.

Before mentioning the findings in this work, we believe it is pertinent to incorporate the words of Arturo Enrique Sampay (1949) on Alberdi and the Constitution "...*Its Argentine acolyte, Juan Bautista Alberdi, principal co-author of the Constitution of 1853, although he did not participate in the Convention of Santa Fe, governed Argentina for almost a hundred years, solely by the vigor of his thought, this great absentee – unraveled the spirit of the fundamental Charter with the following words: The Constitution contains a complete system of economic policy, insofar as it guarantees, by express provisions, the free action of labor, capital and land, as the main agents of production, ratifies the natural law of equilibrium that presides over the phenomenon of the distribution of wealth, and encloses within discrete and fair limits the acts that have a relationship with the phenomenon of public consumption.*"[...] "*Wealth is the daughter of labor, capital, and land, he continues shortly, and as these forces, considered as instruments of production, are nothing more than faculties that man puts into practice to create the means to satisfy the needs of his nature, wealth is the work of man, imposed by the instinct of his conservation and improvement, and obtained by the faculties with which he is endowed to fulfill his destiny in the world...*"¹² The Argentina Constitution of 1853, inspired by liberal principles, has had a great influence on political and economic development. The emphasis on individual freedom, private property and the free market has been an important factor in the economic growth of the region. However, there has also been criticism of economic liberalism, especially for the social inequalities it can generate.

We present the results obtained:

- Centrality of economic growth: Alberdi sees it as the fundamental pillar for the consolidation of independence and progress of South American nations.
- Criticism of traditional constitutional models: The author questions the relevance of these structures, considering them incapable of responding to the challenges and opportunities of the new republics.
- Proposal for a new integrationist model: Alberdi advocates a constitutional model that facilitates the integration of South American nations into the world market, thus promoting trade and regional economic development.
- Innovation in Political Organization: Alberdi proposed a federal and republican structure that was innovative for the time, inspired by successful models such as the American one.

- Primacy of Law and Individual Liberties: he stressed the importance of protecting individual liberties and private property, laying the foundations for a robust rule of law.

- Regional Influence: Alberdi's ideas were fundamental in the drafting of constitutions in countries such as Chile, Peru, Colombia and Mexico, evidencing their regional impact.

- Modernization of the State: he promoted the modernization of the state through the separation of powers and the creation of solid and efficient institutions.

- Alberdi criticizes unitary constitutions: for hindering economic development through restrictions on immigration and foreign capital. He considers that these elements are essential for the progress of Latin America, and highlights the case of the Chilean constitution as a possible exception within the unitary context.

- Women's education: women's education should not focus on ornamental talents such as music or painting, but on preparing them to be dignified and modest, focused on family and home.

- Clergy reform in education: it is proposed that the clergy should not be responsible for the training of lawyers, statesmen, merchants, sailors and warriors, since they cannot instill mercantile and industrial instincts.

- Need to learn English: English is considered essential as the language of freedom, industry and order. It is suggested that it should be mandatory in education to obtain university degrees.

- Combating Social Disintegration: Advocating the use of shared truth and faith as tools to overcome social fragmentation.

- American Identity: Recognition of European Roots: Encourage reflection on American identity, highlighting the fundamental role of civilization and religion of European origin in its formation.

- Homeland as an Integral Concept: Broaden the notion of homeland to encompass not only the physical territory, but also the freedom, order, wealth and civilization rooted in it, elements of European origin.

Conclusions

The research concludes that Juan Bautista Alberdi's ideas in "**Las Bases...**" were not only crucial to the configuration of the Argentina constitutional system, but also significantly influenced the whole of Latin America. His proposals on federalism, protection of individual rights, and modernization of the state remain relevant in the contemporary discussion on constitutional reform in the region. As the region faces new political and social challenges, Alberdi's teachings offer valuable guidance to foster a renewed and more robust constitutional spirit.

The analyzed text presents an innovative and challenging vision on the independence process and the political organization of South American nations. Alberdi's ideas, although contextualized in his time, continue

¹² Sampay Arturo (2007) Informe para la reforma Constitucional de 1949. Carlos Altamirano, Bajo el signo de las masas (1943-1973). Biblioteca del Pensamiento Argentino, Buenos Aires, Emecé, p.2, material otorgado por

la catedra: file:///C:/Users/USUARIO/Downloads/Informe-de-Arturo-Sampay-para-la-reforma-constitucional-de-1949%20(1)%20(2).pdf

to be relevant to the current debate on economic development, regional integration, and the construction of a more prosperous and autonomous Latin America.

We observe a progressive and pragmatic vision of the development of South America, where the need to prioritize material development as a basis for the consolidation of independence and freedom is emphasized. Constitutions, in this context, must be flexible tools that adapt to the changing needs of the region, promoting economic growth and social integration.

Their contribution to education in the region expresses the need for a profound reform for it to be truly beneficial. Therefore, it is crucial to focus on the teaching of applied sciences and arts that allow industrial and practical development, and not so much on moral and philosophical sciences. Education must be directed towards the training of engineers, geologists and naturalists, necessary for the progress of the continent. In addition, the importance of industry as a driver of moralization and order is highlighted. Instruction must be adapted to industrial and commercial life, and English must be an essential part of education. Alberdi outlines a vision of America as a united and prosperous society, based on the recognition of its European heritage and openness to immigration, key elements to achieve a promising future

Perez Gamon C.M. (2024-17) “...*Fernando Benítez's writings offer a critical view of national and popular models. The author recognizes their achievements, but also points out their limitations and errors. This critical view is essential to understanding the history of Latin America and building more just and sustainable development models in the immediate present with a projection into the future...*”. Both Alberdi and Benítez are fundamental authors for understanding the history of Latin America. However, it is through a critical reading of their works and those of other thinkers

that we can build a more complete and complex vision of the historical processes of the region.

As for the validity of Alberdi's proposals, despite having been written in the 19th century, his ideas are still valid today. The principles of federalism, representative republic, separation of powers, individual liberties and rule of law remain fundamental pillars of Latin American democracies. However, it is also important to recognize the challenges faced by democracies in the region, such as social inequality, corruption and violence.

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